

Studies on the 3-Nitrosalicylate Complexes of Zinc(II), Manganese (II) and Iron (II)

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The potentiometric studies showed the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes of each of Zn(II), Mn(II) and Fe(II) with 3-nitrosalicylic acid (3NSA). The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have been determined by half-integral method described by Bjerrum and also by Bjerrum's method of successive approximation and by convergence formula of Schroder for successive approximation. The standard deviations of the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have been determined by the method of least squares. The order of stability is found to be Zn(II) > Fe(II) > Mn(II), in accordance with Irving-Williams rule.

IN continuation of our previous work¹ this communication incorporates the potentiometric study of the formation of 3-nitrosalicylate chelates of Zn(II), Mn(II) and Fe(II). The stepwise formation constants of these chelates have been determined by Bjerrum's method^{2,6}.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either B.D.H., 'AnalaR' or of an equivalent quality.

Standard solutions of the ligand and the metal salts were prepared in double-distilled water.

The solution of ferrous ammonium sulphate was prepared by weighing the required amount of the reagent grade material. To ensure the presence of iron completely in the ferrous state, a small amount of sodium bisulphite was added before addition of the ligand as described by Gould and Vosburgh⁷.

pH of the solutions were measured by using 'Poly-metron CL-41' pH-meter.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric titrations of 1 : 1 mixtures of each of Zn(II), Mn(II) and Fe(II) and 3NSA against alkali show a sharp inflection at two equivalents of alkali. This clearly indicates that the chelation has taken place due to which the protonic hydrogen of the hydroxyl group of 3NSA has been released along with the replacement of the hydrogen from the carboxylic group. The chelation reaction may be represented as :

where M^{2+} stands for Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} or Fe^{2+} .

Titration of 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 mixtures of metal salts and 3NSA against alkali show inflections at approximately four equivalents of alkali which correspond to the formation of only 1 : 2 complex according to the following equation :

The stepwise formation constants of these 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes of Zn(II), Mn(II) and Fe(II) with 3NSA have been determined from the values of \bar{n} and $p[A^{2-}]$, as described by Bjerrum². Since the reagent is insoluble in water, a 25-75% (v/v) water-dioxane solvent was used. A bulk electrolyte of μ 0.1 M sodium perchlorate was adopted to maintain the constant ionic strength. The reaction solutions were all thermostated at $30 \pm 0.2^\circ$. Correction for pH measurements in aqueous-dioxane medium were made as described by Van Uitert and Haas.⁶

In calculating \bar{n} and $p[A^{2-}]$ the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titrations. A series of values for \bar{n} and $p[A^{2-}]$ corresponding to different values of pH were calculated and the formation curves were obtained by plotting \bar{n} values against $p[A^{2-}]$.

The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ for Zn(II)-, Mn(II)-, and Fe(II)-3-nitrosalicylates were directly read from their formation curves. These have been given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL CHELATES OF 3-NITROSALICYLIC ACID : BJERRUM'S METHOD

Metal	At.No.	2nd I.P.	Electro-negativity	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
Zn	30	17.83	1.66	6.74	6.54
Mn	25	15.70	1.60	4.85	4.72
Fe	26	16.16	1.64	5.28	5.05

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The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have also been determined by Bjerrum's method of successive approximation³ and by convergence formula of Schroder for successive approximation⁴. The values so obtained are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF METAL CHELATES OF 3-NITROSALICYLIC ACID : BJERRUM'S METHOD OF SUCCESSIVE APPROXIMATION

Metal	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
Zn	6.70 (6.70)	6.58 (6.58)
Mn	4.82 (4.81)	4.75 (4.75)
Fe	5.25 (5.25)	5.10 (5.08)

The bracketted quantities in Table 2 stand for the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ as determined by Schroder's method of successive approximation.

The standard deviations of the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have also been determined by the method of least squares and are found to be ± 0.03 and ± 0.04 respectively.

Tables 1 and 2 indicate that the $\log K_n$ values follow the order

in accordance with the Irving-Williams rule⁵.

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